

INFORMATION GROWTH: A PANACEA OF CREATIVE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Information growth as a panacea for creative technology is the main focus of this paper. The paper identified some vital areas of information technology as related to creative in technology. Suggestions were made on how to improve this.

INTRODUCTION

Information technology is a modern invention that can give birth to technological creativity through data generation, processing, storage and precision, All these are disseminated into the end users through electronic mechanism. This new trend is indispensable because a nation without information technology will not only become dead but irrelevant in all ramifications while other nations which embrace information technology becomes not only champions but more functional in the scheme of things.

Information technology is now a new order that is accelerating in all facets of human existence, ranging from traditional society to a more technologically developed nation. It is against this development that enhances a new marriage of convenience of a twine concept of information and communication technologies which have changed the traditional system of government to a better functional and challenging ones characterized with a better future.

With advancement in information and communication technology, it now becomes increasingly difficult for a more developing nation to ignore the snail speed-ratio of advancement in the most developing world, if such nation could maintain and sustain creative technological growth. At the wake of development in Information and Communication Technology (ICT), the world over has truly become nothing less than a global village. This new trends in technology is very important as industrial revolution in Europe has a lot of dramatic changes to human's creativity and future growth.

Information Growth: A Panacea of Creative Technology

Similarly information technology does not only provide a major opportunity to developing countries that can access and generate data effectively but not as a threat to those who cannot. In order to achieve optimum benefit, government must evolve well-coordinated plan of ICT programmes that is creative and less biased that will serve as a catalyst in industrial nations of the world for being a national priority which can champion the main cause of this generation to a logical end

Information technology cannot effectively function without particular attention paid to constant electricity supply and reliable telecommunication initiative. In a third world country like ours (Nigeria) effort should be geared towards effective stabilization of light with other facilities like water, telephone, and fax that can make information technology a reality rather than a mystery. One of the dividends of information technology is the rapid technological breakthrough and information revolution that is not only dynamic but also relevant and dependable for reengineering the vision and focus of this generation.

There is no doubt that information technology is a source of transformation and technological creativity which can step up of the socio-economic growth and improve the quality of services within and outside the country.

Information technology as a panacea to creative technological affects directly or indirectly the transfer of goods and services with end products in distance location. Generally speaking, business in all sphere of human endeavours are created and successfully carried out electronically and in a more secured manner across the globe through Internet cyber cafe operation. It is now relevant and possible from any part of the country to increase and export some heart desire products without serious hazards. Creative information technology is contributing immensely especially in areas of educational and learning growth coupled with the precision that is demanding for a genuine data-generation as the backbone of modern society.

For instance a computer can be connected to Internet in a veritable interface between user and the global ocean of information which will provide meaningful result. Apart from the fact that ICT has provided an avenue for optimal utilization of man and human resources in related developments; Telex Education, Medicine, E-health care delivery services are vital areas of interest which creative technology is now inevitable. Besides, it does not reduce the cost

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implication alone but gets the right caliber of manpower in place without changing the base of operation.

IMPROVEMENT ON CREATIVE TECHNOLOGY

It is very relevant to note that creative technology is not only a way out of poverty alleviation and eradication but also a source of job creation and opportunities for arresting brain drain. This is not all, the instability of government is very inimical to policy-sustainability which easily become the product of creative technology. In improving and maintaining creative technology, the followings are necessary:

1. Youths should be empowered through various programmes in the anticipation of the challenges in information and communication technology as a drive towards purposeful creativity.
2. A national policy on technological growth and creativity should be fashioned out to assist in the proper take-off development programme for the present generation.
3. The need for a well-integrated creative system to enhance information technological at various levels of the education system.
4. Accessibility to scientific data via Internet and worldwide websites as parts of immediate step to improve the information needs and consciousness of people.
5. The government should be discouraged as the sole monopoly of globalisation of infrastructural and information facilities (GII).

CONCLUSION

To sanitize the nation, the government should re-direct its policy to give opportunity to all the citizenry in order to improve the quality of lives and services rendered in all human endeavours. Besides, the nation, particularly the populace is required to be a new orientation towards better direction of technological development that could provide the country the chance to compete favourably with others in advanced countries. Minus this, our educational and social life should be such that can make individual develop in order to master its own environment.

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